

DEVELOPING STUDENTS' SENSE OF RESPONSIBILITY FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

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ANNOTATION: This article discusses the current issue, namely, the importance of educating students in a sense of environmental awareness, society and general responsibility, and the importance of preserving the purity of the atmosphere as an important source for creating a healthy environment in the future.

KEYWORDS: Ecological education, ecological education, flora and fauna, ecological outlook, atmospheric air, public health, nature protection.

INTRODUCTION: Promoting long-term environmental commitments. Environmental education should instill a sense of responsibility beyond the classroom, in students' daily lives and future careers. By adopting these strategies, teachers can create a comprehensive and effective environmental education program that equips students with the knowledge, skills, and motivation to become environmentally conscious and responsible citizens.

Educational technologies can play a crucial role in developing environmental education in students, instilling a sense of responsibility and respect for nature. Here are some technologies and approaches that can be used to strengthen environmental education through the conservation and use of nature:

Today's education has set itself the main goal of not only imparting knowledge, but also providing spiritual and economic education. Therefore, it should be noted at this point that the use of oriental wisdom in education, especially in the primary school, in the spirit of raising the young generation in the spirit of respect for the fascinating and attractive nature and flora, is very effective. The upbringing given in the family in terms of love and respect for the fascinating and attractive nature and flora is imprinted in the hearts of children for a lifetime. One of the main tasks is to pass on the product of their upbringing to the future generation - their children.

Therefore, today's school teachers are faced with the task of forming an attitude to nature and ecological awareness among younger schoolchildren, aimed at the absence of contradictions between man and nature. The main task of such

education is to form a positive personal attitude to the environment in students, as well as to increase the child's place in nature and its role in its preservation. Therefore, methodological work, expanding the scope of scientific research in this area, and developing methodological manuals and recommendations for teachers are important in ensuring the quality of environmental education. Education in the "broad sense" is an objective process that occurs in society without depending on will, a social process. Education in the "narrow sense" is a conscious and planned influence on a child by adults or a special social institution. It is especially relevant to teach students to protect nature on the basis of creating a new generation of integrative programs in ecology in the system of continuing education.

Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR):

Use AR and VR apps to simulate virtual journeys that allow students to explore different ecosystems, wildlife habitats, and natural wonders. Create immersive experiences that demonstrate the impact of human activities on the environment and encourage awareness and responsibility.

Online Learning Platforms:

Develop interactive online courses and modules that cover various aspects of environmental science, conservation, and sustainability. Use multimedia elements such as videos, animations, and quizzes to engage students in a fun and informative way.

Mobile Apps:

Create educational apps that encourage outdoor exploration and learning. Apps can provide information about local flora and fauna, promote nature walks, and offer interactive challenges related to environmental protection. Add features like geotagging and citizen science projects to engage students in collecting real-world data.

Social media and gamification:

Use social media platforms and gamification to create environmental challenges and competitions. Encourage students to share their environmental initiatives, nature photos, or environmentally conscious practices on social media, fostering a sense of community and shared responsibility. Online Collaboration Tools:

Use collaboration tools to facilitate group projects and discussions about environmental issues. Platforms like Google Workspace or Microsoft Teams allow students to work together on research, presentations, and action plans. Develop online communities where students can share ideas, resources, and success stories related to environmental protection.

Interactive Maps and Geospatial Technologies:

Use interactive maps and geospatial technologies to show the impact of climate change, deforestation, and other environmental issues on specific areas. Encourage students to explore and analyze real-world data, helping them understand the interconnectedness of ecosystems.

Sensor Technologies:

Integrate sensor technologies to monitor environmental parameters such as air quality, water quality, and biodiversity in local areas. Engage students in collecting and analyzing data from these sensors, providing them with hands-on experience in environmental monitoring.

E-books and digital resources:

Develop e-books and digital resources covering topics such as conservation practices, sustainable living, and the importance of biodiversity. Make these resources easily accessible to students, teachers, and parents to promote continuous learning beyond the classroom.

Robotics and drones:

Integrate robotics and drones into environmental education to explore remote or hard-to-reach areas, observe wildlife, and assess environmental changes. Engage students in building and programming simple environmental monitoring robots or drones as part of STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) initiatives. By combining these technologies, teachers can create dynamic and engaging learning environments that not only provide knowledge, but also instill a deep appreciation for nature and a commitment to its conservation.

CONCLUSION: It should be noted that our national values never become obsolete, the formation of ecological education of young people, the development of their attitude to the environment, and ecological culture is a requirement of the time. This methodological manual is dedicated to teaching environmental protection, based on our rich pedagogical heritage of the past, and shows the continuity of the relationship between nature, man, and society, that man is always connected with nature, that man cannot live without nature.

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